

STUDIES ON GENETIC VARIABILITY AND HERITABILITY FOR YIELD AND YIELD CONTRIBUTING CHARACTERS IN OKRA (*Abelmoschus esculentus* (L.) Moench)D.K.Zate¹, Faria Khan², Shelke S. A³ and Bastewad .V.S⁴.¹Assist. Professor, Department of Agril., Botany, VNMKV Parbhani, Maharashtra, India.²Assist. Professor, Department of Entomology, VNMKV Parbhani Maharashtra, India.³M.Sc (Agri) student, Department of Agril., Botany, VNMKV Parbhani, Maharashtra, India.⁴Assist. Professor, College of Agriculture, VNMKV Parbhani, Maharashtra, India.

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Abstract:

The present investigation was conducted to evaluate genetic variability and heritability in 52 okra accessions received from NBPGR, New Delhi based on yield and yield contributing characters, as genetic variability in any crop is pre-requisite for selection of superior genotypes over the existing cultivars. Knowledge of variability and heritability of yield and its contributing characters helps in the selection of appropriate strategy for a breeding programme for evolving superior varieties. In the present experiment, analysis of variance shows that there is considerable difference between the genotypes for all the characters under study. The result of genetic parameters revealed that moderate to high PCV, GCV, high heritability accompanied with high genetic advance was recorded for the characters number of fruits per plant, fruit weight, fruit length, fruit girth, number of ridges per fruit, plant height, number of branches per plant, internodal length, number of seeds per fruit, 100 seeds weight and yield per plant. This indicating that the selection would be effective for these characters to bring genetic enhancement in desired way.

Key words: Okra, Variability, Heritability, Genetic advance

Introduction:

Okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* (L.) Moench) is an important vegetable crop grown all over India and tropical and sub tropical parts of the world. The green tender fruits of okra are good source of carbohydrate, protein, vitamins (A, B and C) and rich in calcium, potassium and other mineral matters. It contains 1.9 g protein, 1.2 g fiber, 1.5 mg Fe and 88 IU Vitamin A per 100 g of edible portion. Genetic improvement of any crop mainly depends on the amount of genetic variability present in the population and the germplasm serves as a valuable source of base population and provide scope for wide variability. Heritability is the heritable portion of phenotypic variance. Heritable variation can be effectively used with greater degree of accuracy when heritability is studied in conjunction with genetic advance (Johnson et al., 1955). Extent of variability present in the crop becomes a pre-requisite as it provides basis for variety development by effective selection and also for selecting desirable genotypes needed for further crop improvement programs. Coefficient of variation is useful in the assessment of genetic variability for the particular character. Heritability denotes the proportion of phenotypic variation due to genotypes thus helps the breeders to select the elite variety for a character. Genetic advance denotes the improvement in the mean genotypic values of selected families over base population and thus helps breeder to select the progenies in the earlier generation itself.

Material And Methods:

The present experiment was undertaken to study genetic variability and heritability for yield and yield contributing characters in fifty two genotypes of okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* (L.) Moench) including two checks.

Fifty two genotypes of okra including two checks were sown during kharif 2020 in Randomized Block Design with two replications. The experiment was conducted at research farm, Breeder Seeds Production Unit, VNMKV, Parbhani. All the recommended cultural practices and packages were applied for growing healthy and good crop. In each genotype line, five plants were randomly selected from each replication and observations were recorded for days to 50 per cent flowering, number of days to first harvest, number of fruits per plant, fruit weight (g), fruit length (cm), fruit girth (cm), number of ridges per fruit, number of nodes per plant, plant height (cm), number of branches per plant, internodal length (cm), number of seeds per fruit, 100 seed weight (g) and yield per plant (g). The data were statistically analyzed for the analysis of variance as per the standard statistical procedure. The variability parameters were estimated as per the procedure given by Panse and Sukhatme (1985), co-efficient of variation was calculated by the formulae given by Burton (1952), Heritability in broad sense and genetic advance were estimated by the

formula given by Johnson et al. (1955) and Allard (1960) respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Considerable genetic variability among fifty two genotypes was observed for characters in okra are furnished in Table 1. Analysis of variance for various yield and yield contributing characters have shown highly significant differences among all the fourteen characters under study viz., days to 50 per cent flowering, number of days to first harvest, number of fruits per plant, fruit weight (g), fruit length (cm), fruit girth (cm), number of ridges per fruit, number of nodes per plant, plant height (cm), number of branches per plant, internodal length (cm), number of seeds per fruit, 100 seed weight (g) and yield per plant (g). This indicated presence of considerable amount of genetic variability among the genotypes and there is ample scope for exploitation of all the above characters.

The findings were similar with Walling et al. (2020) for plant height, number of branches per plant, number of fruits per plant, fruit length, fruit diameter and yield per plant. Rambabu et al. (2019) for plant height, number of branches per plant, internodal length, days to 50% flowering, number of days to first harvest, fruit length (cm), fruit girth (cm), fruit weight (g), number of fruits per plant, number of seeds per fruit, 100 seed weight and yield per plant. Khajuria et al. (2015) for fruit length, fruit girth, number of fruits per plant, fruit weight, number of seeds per fruit and 100 seed weight.

Genetic and phenotypic coefficient of variation, Heritability and Genetic advance

The range of variation and the estimates of genetic parameters which include coefficient of variation (GCV and PCV), heritability in broad sense and genetic advance are presented in Table 3. The magnitude of PCV was higher than GCV for all the characters studied showing that there is relative resistance to environmental changes. The marked effect of environmental factors for the phenotype expression of genotypes was poor than the greater chance of improving these traits through selection depends on the output of phenotypes. However, difference between them was not of high magnitude. The range was highest for yield per plant (107.48- 355.40) followed by plant height (96.95-176.00), number of seeds per fruit (42.00-160.00), number of days to first harvest (46.50-60.00), days to 50 per cent flowering (42.50-54.50), number of nodes per plant (10.90-20.60), fruit weight (10.75-32.00), fruit length (8.84-19.30), number of fruits per plant (7.50-19.50), number of ridges per fruit (5.00-10.00) and internodal length (4.33-10.70). Lowest range was recorded for 100 seed weight (1.75-9.00), fruit girth (1.30-3.90) and number of branches per plant (1.20-2.35). In the present investigation high estimates of genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation were observed for number of fruits per plant (23.77, 24.48), fruit weight

(24.23, 25.11), fruit girth (21.07, 22.61), number of ridges per fruit (26.99, 27.47), number of seeds per fruit (34.33, 34.87), 100 seeds weight (28.68, 31.22) and yield per plant (30.17, 30.37). The high values of GCV and PCV indicates that there was a chance of improvement of these charactersthrough direct selection. Moderate PCV and GCV values were recorded for fruit length (18.06, 19.08), number of nodes per plant (10.49, 13.01), plant height (15.03, 15.65), number of branches per plant (13.47, 16.81) and internodal length (17.72, 19.30). While lower values of phenotypic and genotypic coefficient of variation were observed for days to 50 per cent flowering (6.43, 6.65) and number of days to first harvest (5.98, 6.26). These results are in agreement with the results reported by workers Walling N. *et al.* (2020), Rambabu B. *et al.* (2019), Vishnu Priyanka D. *et al.* (2018), Khalid Syfullah *et al.* (2018), Thulasiram L. B. *et al.* (2017), Chandramouli *et al.* (2016), Kumar Awadhesh (2016), Khajuria R. K. *et al.* (2015), Mishra Archana *et al.* (2015), Alake C. O. (2012), Das *et al.* (2012), Nwangburuka C.C. *et al.* (2012), Adeoluwa O. O. and Kehinde O. B. (2011).

The effectiveness of selection for any character depend not only the extent of genetic variability but also in the extent to which it will be transferred from one generation to the next generation. The genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation alone does not show the proportion of total heritable variation. The heritability and genetic advance as per cent of mean estimates are better indicators in this respect. High value of heritability in broad sense were recorded for all the characters under study *viz.*, days to 50 per cent flowering (93.5), number of days to first harvest (91.0), number of fruits per plant (94.2), fruit weight (93.1), fruit length (89.6), fruit girth (86.8), number of ridges per fruit (96.6), number of nodes per plant (65.1), plant height (92.2), number of branches per plant (64.3), internodal length (84.3), number of seeds per fruit (96.9), 100 seed weight (84.4) and yield per plant (98.7). High value of genetic advance as per cent of mean was recorded for number of fruits per plant (47.54), fruit weight (48.17), fruit length (35.21), fruit girth (40.44), number of ridges per fruit (54.65), plant height (29.73), number of branches per plant (22.26), internodal length(33.51), number of seeds per fruit (69.62), 100 seed weight (54.28) and yield per plant (61.74), while moderate values of genetic advance as per cent of mean were recorded for days to 50 per cent flowering (12.81), number of days to first harvest (11.75) and number of nodes per plant (17.44) in the present study. High value of heritability for all characters under study, which is in accordance with the studies of Rambabu B. *et al.* (2019), Thulasiram L. B. *et al.* (2017), Phanikrishna M. *et al.* (2015). Similar results were reported by Walling N. *et al.* (2020), Khalid Syfullah *et al.* (2018) and Chandramouli B. *et al.* (2016) for genetic advances as per cent of mean. It was advised that the importance of considering both heritability and genetic advance as per cent mean for characters individually in determining how much progress can be made through selection (Johnson *et al.* 1955). The heritability accompanied with genetic advance as per cent mean is more effective for predicting yield under phenotypicselection than heritability estimates alone. The traits number of fruits per plant, fruit weight, fruit length, fruit girth, number of ridges per fruit, number of branches per plant, plant height, internodal length, number of seeds per fruit, 100 seed weight and yield per plant shows high estimates of heritability accompanied with high genetic advance as per cent mean indicating additive gene action and thus selection for these characters in genetically diverse material would be effective for desired genetic improvement. The characters days to 50 per cent flowering, number of days to first harvest and number of nodes per plant shows high heritability accompanied with moderate genetic advance as per cent mean. Similar results were reported by Walling N. *et al.* (2020), Agbowuro *et al.* (2019), Rambabu B. *et al.* (2019),Khalid Syfullah *et al.* (2018), Mallesh *et al.* (2018), Thulasiram L. B. *et al.* (2017), Neeraj singh *et al.* (2017), Phanikrishna *et al.* (2015), Ahamed *et al.* (2015) and Morey *et al.* (2012). Thus, the estimates of genetic parameters like PCV, GCV, heritability and genetic advance altogether it is evident

that the traits *viz.*, number of fruits perplant, fruit weight, fruit girth, number of ridges per fruit, number of seeds per fruit, 100 seeds weight and yield per plant which show high value for PCV, GCV, heritability and genetic advance as per cent mean were considered most valuable and selection of these traits couldbe more effective for improving grain yield in okra.

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Table 1: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for fourteen characters in Okra

Sr. No.	Characters	Mean Sum of Square		
		Replication (1 d. f.)	Treatment (51 d. f.)	Error (51 d. f.)
1	Days to 50% flowering	0.00	19.66***	0.65
2	Number of days to first harvest	0.77	20.78***	0.97
3	Number of fruits per plant	0.11	22.04***	0.65
4	Fruit weight (g)	0.02	35.35***	1.25
5	Fruit length (cm)	0.05	13.60***	0.74
6	Fruit girth (g)	0.02	0.30***	0.02
7	Number of ridges per fruit	0.00	5.61***	0.09
8	Number of nodes per plant	12.04**	6.34***	1.34
9	Plant height (cm)	70.32	940.87***	38.27
10	Number of branches per plant	0.02	0.13***	0.02
11	Internodal length (cm)	0.23	4.05***	0.34
12	Number of seeds per fruit	0.00	1120.04***	17.59
13	100 seed weight (g)	0.00	4.68***	0.39
14	Yield per plant (g)	12.50	9316.66***	61.74

Table 2 The mean performance of fourteen characters studied in okra.

Sr No	Genotypes	DFP	NDFH	NFPF	FW	FL	FG	NRPF	NNPP	PH	NBPP	IL	NSPF	HSW	YPP
1	Pusa sawani	46.50	51.50	14.50	14.25	11.28	1.65	5.00	15.80	147.80	2.15	6.18	42.00	6.00	212.85
2	IC 1543	46.50	50.50	18.80	18.00	18.40	1.90	5.00	15.80	166.00	2.35	10.70	58.20	5.50	319.65
3	IC 3302	47.50	51.50	17.50	17.30	14.90	1.75	5.00	16.20	168.51	1.70	10.00	50.80	5.00	298.75
4	IC 3340-C	47.50	53.00	10.10	16.95	12.96	1.75	7.00	14.80	108.25	1.30	6.85	66.70	3.00	158.52
5	IC 3759	46.50	51.00	13.10	15.05	14.21	1.90	5.00	16.10	149.20	1.75	7.98	48.20	3.50	193.35
6	IC 3769	47.50	52.50	12.70	17.85	12.98	1.65	5.00	15.10	128.00	1.40	8.49	50.50	4.50	228.30
7	IC 3769A	47.50	52.00	17.10	18.95	16.30	1.65	5.00	15.00	166.00	1.75	9.55	59.30	6.50	315.00
8	IC 4328	46.50	51.50	12.50	12.90	12.50	1.75	5.00	13.60	117.50	1.50	7.45	52.60	7.00	155.00
9	IC 4378	45.50	50.00	12.80	12.70	15.25	1.65	5.00	12.80	137.50	1.20	9.07	50.60	5.50	157.80
10	IC 4507	47.50	52.00	17.50	18.30	15.31	1.60	5.00	18.10	162.00	1.70	9.10	56.00	4.00	316.00
11	IC 6376-B	45.00	50.00	17.50	19.50	17.15	1.75	5.00	15.80	164.30	1.50	8.75	66.60	3.00	335.45
12	IC 6485	42.50	46.50	13.90	19.00	14.94	1.65	5.00	15.00	140.50	1.50	8.38	60.00	6.50	243.37
13	IC 7452	44.50	49.50	12.80	14.85	11.90	1.85	5.00	12.50	130.00	1.30	8.99	57.40	3.50	180.40
14	IC 7472	44.50	49.50	11.00	14.02	12.55	1.60	5.00	13.90	107.50	1.90	6.03	60.40	3.00	131.20
15	IC 7473	45.50	50.00	17.90	15.80	18.90	1.70	5.00	16.85	162.30	1.50	8.50	50.20	5.50	272.20
16	IC 7856-A	45.50	50.00	9.70	12.80	11.87	1.35	5.00	14.00	156.60	1.50	7.08	54.80	3.60	132.65
17	IC 7952	43.50	48.00	9.60	11.55	11.02	1.40	5.00	10.90	112.10	1.50	5.56	47.40	1.75	112.50
18	IC 8991	43.00	48.00	13.00	16.40	14.03	1.55	5.50	14.00	143.00	1.50	9.80	57.40	6.50	200.10
19	IC 8991-A	45.50	51.00	16.00	17.50	14.79	1.70	7.50	14.20	159.90	1.50	8.76	64.30	4.50	287.93
20	IC 9327	45.50	50.50	14.15	14.85	13.03	1.70	5.00	12.85	123.45	1.20	7.09	51.40	3.50	198.40
21	IC 9856	43.00	47.50	15.35	11.65	8.84	1.75	5.00	13.60	113.25	1.30	6.89	59.40	3.00	183.20
22	IC 9856-B	47.50	51.50	12.80	12.50	10.24	1.85	8.50	12.00	107.30	1.70	7.16	74.80	4.50	156.20
23	IC 9856-C	48.50	53.50	15.25	17.75	14.88	1.60	7.00	16.30	130.50	1.70	8.00	62.40	3.00	261.10
24	IC 10252	48.50	53.00	16.00	16.35	16.38	1.60	7.50	13.70	152.50	1.75	8.75	79.95	5.50	257.50
25	IC 10256A	51.50	56.50	16.50	14.05	13.42	1.70	5.00	13.75	145.00	1.70	8.85	69.30	6.50	228.00
26	IC 11533	48.50	53.00	12.20	10.75	12.30	1.30	5.00	13.50	117.50	1.55	8.70	58.50	5.50	133.30
27	Parbhani Kranti	44.50	49.00	15.85	13.85	13.20	1.60	5.00	16.00	159.00	1.50	8.15	48.40	6.00	227.40
28	EC 305643	45.50	50.50	9.20	13.20	12.78	1.55	5.00	13.00	96.95	1.80	6.46	45.30	5.00	120.25
29	EC 305635	46.50	52.00	19.50	18.00	19.30	1.70	5.00	16.70	176.00	1.70	8.28	49.10	5.50	337.50
30	EC 305613	48.50	53.50	15.20	15.50	16.85	1.80	7.00	13.50	158.50	1.90	9.40	42.40	4.50	231.00

** Significant at 1 per cent level of probability or level of significance

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Sr No	Genotypes	DDF	NDFH	NFPP	FW	FL	FG	NRPF	NNPP	PH	NBPP	IL	NSPF	HSW	YPP
31	EC 305634	47.50	51.50	13.80	18.75	16.55	1.65	5.00	14.00	162.50	1.70	8.21	53.90	5.50	247.00
32	EC 305652	45.50	49.50	17.50	18.95	16.48	1.75	5.00	15.20	172.25	1.70	9.23	55.20	3.00	310.50
33	EC 305653	47.50	52.50	19.50	18.75	17.15	1.60	5.00	17.35	175.00	1.50	9.07	60.40	6.50	355.40
34	EC 305664	46.00	50.50	15.90	12.00	12.55	1.80	10.00	14.00	113.45	2.00	7.23	50.80	5.50	187.80
35	EC 305672	45.50	50.00	15.85	16.60	13.04	1.55	5.00	15.90	160.15	1.60	6.31	59.30	7.50	251.00
36	EC 305675	45.50	50.00	18.05	16.80	17.10	1.50	5.00	16.00	175.80	1.90	9.00	59.30	6.50	276.50
37	EC 305685	50.50	55.50	9.90	22.00	17.38	2.10	9.00	15.60	128.00	1.60	6.78	101.50	9.00	208.90
38	EC 305687	51.00	55.50	11.50	21.80	15.59	1.90	9.50	17.10	128.90	1.70	6.59	160.00	5.25	238.70
39	EC 305689	49.50	55.50	12.90	20.30	15.10	1.65	9.00	16.90	141.70	1.70	5.90	99.30	6.00	247.50
40	EC 305691	52.50	57.50	11.00	23.05	12.98	1.90	8.50	15.40	133.65	2.10	6.74	104.60	6.00	234.40
41	EC 305609	53.50	58.50	19.50	17.65	17.39	1.85	5.00	16.90	171.05	1.70	9.22	70.60	4.50	299.60
42	EC 305612	49.50	54.50	18.35	17.35	16.00	2.00	5.00	15.00	149.30	1.70	7.21	73.30	7.50	291.25
43	EC 305694	54.50	60.00	10.70	21.50	14.84	2.05	9.00	20.60	140.70	1.50	4.71	98.50	4.50	216.45
44	EC 305714	52.50	57.00	7.50	14.50	11.73	1.70	5.00	16.40	108.50	2.10	5.26	77.80	5.00	110.70
45	EC 305716	53.50	58.50	9.15	10.75	9.83	1.75	5.00	15.60	140.20	1.60	6.04	85.50	3.50	107.90
46	EC 305741	52.50	56.50	9.80	23.10	13.12	2.10	7.50	16.90	136.20	1.90	8.08	117.80	5.50	222.05
47	EC 305745	53.50	58.50	12.90	21.30	16.80	2.10	9.00	18.30	134.20	2.30	4.33	94.50	4.00	249.10
48	EC 305764	52.50	56.50	9.50	32.00	9.80	3.90	9.50	15.70	158.00	1.80	8.16	125.60	8.50	295.80
49	EC 305766	52.50	57.00	13.20	19.00	13.50	2.10	8.00	13.00	125.30	1.70	6.38	73.80	5.00	243.10
50	EC 306709	49.50	54.00	8.00	12.70	10.04	1.35	8.50	13.70	133.60	1.90	6.41	94.30	3.50	107.48
51	EC 305731	48.50	53.00	9.20	16.10	10.54	1.55	5.00	13.60	107.60	1.80	6.83	53.20	7.00	142.17
52	EC 305768	51.50	56.00	11.70	29.00	9.87	2.90	7.50	15.20	146.00	1.30	6.93	92.60	5.25	295.00
	Mean	47.91	52.62	13.75	17.03	14.03	1.78	6.15	15.07	141.32	1.67	7.68	68.38	5.10	225.44
	C.V.	1.69	1.87	5.87	6.58	6.16	8.22	5.08	7.68	4.371	10.05	7.65	6.13	12.33	3.48
	SE+	0.57	0.69	0.57	0.79	0.61	0.10	0.22	0.81	4.37	0.11	0.41	2.96	0.44	5.55
	CD at 5%	1.62	1.98	1.62	2.25	1.73	0.29	0.62	2.32	12.41	0.33	1.18	8.42	1.26	15.77

DDF- Days to 50% Flowering , NFPP- Number of fruits per plant, FW – Weight of fruit (g) , FL – Fruit length(cm) , FG- Fruit girth(cm) , NRPF-Number of ridges per fruit , NNPF-Number of nodes per fruit, PH-Plant height (cm), NBPP-Number of branches per plant, IL- Internodal length, NSPF- Number of seed per fruit, HSP- 100 Seed weight (g), YPP- Yield per plant (g)

Table 3: Mean, range, genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV), phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV), heritability and genetic advance for fourteen characters studied in okra

Sr. No.	Characters	Range Maximum	Range maximum	Mean	$\sigma^2(g)$ Genotypic variance	$\sigma^2(p)$ Phenotypic variance	GCV%	PCV%	h^2 b.s. (%)	GA	GA as % of mean
1	Days to 50% flowering	42.50	54.50	47.91	9.50	10.15	6.43	6.65	93.5	6.14	12.81
2	Number of days to first harvest	46.50	60.00	52.62	9.90	10.87	5.98	6.26	91.0	6.18	11.75
3	Number of fruits per plant	7.50	19.50	13.75	10.69	11.34	23.77	24.48	94.2	6.54	47.54
4	Fruit weight (g)	10.75	32.00	17.03	17.05	18.30	24.23	25.11	93.1	8.20	48.17
5	Fruit length (cm)	8.84	19.30	14.03	6.42	7.17	18.06	19.08	89.6	4.94	35.21
6	Fruit girth (cm)	1.30	3.90	1.78	0.14	0.16	21.07	22.61	86.8	0.72	40.44
7	Number of ridges per fruit	5.00	10.00	6.15	2.76	2.85	26.99	27.47	96.6	3.36	54.65
8	Number of nodes per plant	10.90	20.60	15.07	2.50	3.84	10.49	13.01	65.1	2.63	17.44
9	Plant height (cm)	96.95	176.00	141.32	451.30	489.57	15.03	15.65	92.2	42.01	29.73
10	Number of branches per plant	1.20	2.35	1.67	0.05	0.07	13.47	16.81	64.3	0.37	22.26
11	Internodal length (cm)	4.33	10.70	7.68	1.85	2.20	17.72	19.30	84.3	2.57	33.51
12	Number of seeds per fruit	42.00	160.00	68.38	551.22	568.82	34.33	34.87	96.9	47.61	69.62
13	100 seed weight (g)	1.75	9.00	5.10	2.14	2.53	28.68	31.22	84.4	2.77	54.28
14	Yield per plant (g)	107.48	355.40	225.44	4627.46	4689.20	30.17	30.37	98.7	139.20	61.74